

The effect of government roles, family education, and community attitudes on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City, Indonesia

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Abstract

This research is aimed at analyzing (1) the effect of government roles on community attitudes in Gorontalo City, (2) the effect of family education on community attitudes in Gorontalo City, (3) the effect of community attitudes on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City, (4) the effect of government roles on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City, (5) the effect of family education on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City, and (6) the simultaneous effect of government roles, family education, and community attitudes on juvenile delinquency. The method was a survey using a quantitative approach with path analysis. The population covered all adolescents in Gorontalo City, 15,342 in number. 99 adolescents acted as samples. Data were collected through questionnaire distribution.

The conclusions were: (1) Government roles had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 62% on community attitudes. That was, the higher the government roles, the higher the community attitudes, (2) Family education had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 71.8% on community attitudes. That was, the higher the family education, the higher the community attitudes, (3) Community attitudes had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 65.3% on juvenile delinquency. That was, the higher the community attitudes, the lower the juvenile delinquency, (4) Government roles had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 43.2% on juvenile delinquency. That was, the higher the government roles, the lower the juvenile delinquency, (5) Family education had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 73% on juvenile delinquency. That was, the higher the family education, the lower the juvenile delinquency, and (6) Government roles, family education, and community attitudes had a simultaneous, direct, positive, and significant effect of 76.6% on juvenile delinquency. That was, the higher the government roles, the lower the juvenile delinquency. Accordingly, higher government roles, family education, and family attitudes would simultaneously bring about lower juvenile delinquency. In other words, higher government roles, family education, and community attitudes would simultaneously bring about lower juvenile delinquency.

Keywords: Government Role; Family Education; Community Attitudes; Juvenile Delinquency

1. Introduction

Some forms of juvenile delinquency we can frequently encounter in Gorontalo City are fighting, wandering around, truancy from schools, leaving home without permission, premarital sex, and grouping. The last is commonly known as genk-genk remaja (youth gangs). The gangs orient their daily activities to negative deeds, e.g., drinking alcohol, sniffing Aibon glue, illegal racing, thefts, fights between gangs, and archery targeted at people.

Juvenile delinquency reportedly increased in 2019 to 791, dominated by drunkenness and theft. In 2020, the number even increased to 872, in which there was a surge in drunkenness (drinking alcohol and sniffing Aibon glue) and theft but a decline in illegal racing. In 2021, the number also increased to 1,046 cases, predominated by drunkenness.

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Several factors known to impact juvenile delinquency are government roles, family education, and community attitudes. The government functions as a community protector, builder, servant, and participation activator. The urban village community, either in groups or individually, is in need of services to fulfill needs it cannot meet independently, such as health services, education, jobs, marriage, inheritance, birth, and permission.

From my observation of juvenile delinquency settlement in Gorontalo City, the Gorontalo City government has issued Gorontalo City Regulation Number 7/2016 concerning Protection for Women and Children from Violence, Gorontalo City Regulation Number 1/2018 concerning Public Order, and Gorontalo City Regulation Number 7/2019 concerning Child-Friendly City Implementation. Besides, the Gorontalo City Government forms an urban security task force comprising civil service police units. This task force is responsible for securing and rading places considered vulnerable areas where adolescents commit negative actions, e.g., drinking alcohol, consuming drugs, and others. The urban village-level government consists of three pillars: the urban village head, BABINSA, and BABINKANTIBMAS, responsible for handling urban-village-level issues.

My observation in Gorontalo City attested to that some families gave no education to adolescents. Parents allowed their adolescent children to go out at night and hang out with their friends till late. Furthermore, they had inadequate control of their adolescent children's activities outside home. Some of them even left all educational affairs of their children to specific educational institutions. The phenomena excite juvenile delinquency in either educational, family, or community environments.

Additionally, there was a direct communication gap between the community and adolescents. The second party was busy mingling with peers and playing games, decreasing their intensity of communication with the community in general. In addition, rapid technology and communication development bring on rapid acceptance of information among adolescents, causing direct control of the community on them to grow more complex. Adolescents can plan activities through social media groups or carry out direct movements without their parents knowing. The activities may be caught after the crime is successfully executed.

Juvenile delinquency is the responsibility of all parties, from parents, the community, to the local government. Several factors engendering juvenile delinquency are a lack of attention and guidance from parents and economic factors. Parents and the government are both involved in adolescent management.

Based on the explanation, I performed research on the effect of government roles, family education, and community attitudes on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City.

1.1. Research Problems

Building on problem limitation, the research problems are:

- Do government roles affect community attitudes in Gorontalo City?
- Does family education affect community attitudes in Gorontalo City?
- Do community attitudes affect juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City?
- Do government roles affect juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City?
- Does family education affect juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City?
- Do government roles, family education, and community attitudes affect juvenile delinquency simultaneously?

1.2. Research Objectives

The research is aimed at:

- Examining the effect of government roles on community attitudes in Gorontalo City.
- Examining the effect of family education on community attitudes in Gorontalo City.
- Examining the effect of community attitudes on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City.
- Examining the effect of government roles on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City.
- Examining the effect of family education on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City.
- Examining the simultaneous effect of government roles, family education, and community attitudes on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City.

2. Theoretical Review

2.1. Juvenile Delinquency

Juvenile delinquency refers to a broad range, from socially unacceptable behaviors (such as behaving excessively at schools), status violations (such as running away), to criminal acts (such as theft). Behaviors categorized as delinquency, classified as abnormal, and expansively undertaken were behavioral disorders (Santrock, 2017:32).

Kartono (2017:96) argues that juvenile delinquency, constituting evil behaviors (dursilah) or crimes/delinquency of young people, is a symptom of social illness (pathology) in children and adolescents because of a form of social neglect, generating their deviant behaviors. Walgito (2003) limits juvenile delinquency definition to law-violating acts committed by children, especially adolescents. The same acts by adults are called criminal acts.

Grounded on those definitions, I can conclude that juvenile delinquency is a violation committed by young people reaching adulthood and that the act violates the order of values determined by the community or people in general. The act is a product of social neglect and encourages adolescents to make standards for their behaviors.

Kartono (2017:85) divides juvenile delinquency behaviors into four, i.e.:

- Isolated juvenile delinquency
- Neurotic juvenile delinquency
- Psychopathic juvenile delinquency
- Moral defect juvenile delinquency

On the grounds of the explanation, juvenile delinquency refers to a violation, attack, mistake, or crime which is considered relatively minor and against the legal law. It is committed by non-adult children and comes with the indicators: isolated delinquency, neurotic delinquency, psychopathic delinquency, and moral defect delinquency.

2.2. Government Role

According to Nuramelia (2016:7), a government constitutes an organization authorized in policy-making in the form of laws applicable to certain areas under their authorization. A government, in an extended definition, is an organization working by running government systems, i.e., executive, legislative, and judicial. A government, in a narrow definition, refers to an association body applying policies to manage and regulate a governance system.

Fatih (2014:13) conveys that a government constitutes an organization authorized to make and implement laws in particular areas. Suradinata, in Fatih (2014:13), defines a government as an organization with great power in a country, wherein the power encompasses community, territorial, and power affairs to attain the country goals. Affan, in Fatih (2014:13), describes a government as an organized activity concerned about the people of the country predicated on the National principle and originating from sovereignty to realize social objectives in interested areas.

Yusuf (2014:5) states that as regards empowerment, a government functions to lead the people to independence and development, generating prosperity instead of burdening the people with them. People call for optimized government roles to build a community. Among the roles are:

- The government as a regulator
- The government as a dynamic-making
- The government as a facilitator

From the above definitions, a local government acts as a tool in a governance implementation system. A local government refers to an administrative authority in a specific area smaller than a country. For example, Indonesia constitutes a country with divided areas as provinces. The provincial areas are divided into district and city areas. Each provincial, district, and city area has a local government regulated by laws.

2.3. Family Education

Education, as part of human needs, plays a critical role in creating advanced civilization. Hence, a conceptual base is needed to make education laden with values, prevent the emergence of destroyers in its implementation, and create a solihun li zamanin wa makanin (up-to-date) one (Baharun, 2019:54).

Educational goals are set by individuals and achieved through efforts. Another argument defines educational goals as the expected changes in educated changes after experiencing an educational process. The changes can be reflected through their behaviors, personal life, or social and environmental life where they exist (Langgulong, 2015:146).

An educational goal is also a description of a principle or view of humans, either individually or in groups. Addressing educational goals will engage with value and norm systems within a cultural context, in either myths, beliefs, religions, philosophy, ideologies, and so forth (Aziz, 2015:72).

In so doing, educational goals refer to maintaining and protecting children, allowing them to grow and develop well. A family is a shared living unity mainly familiarized by children, hence acquiring the name of the main educational environment. The early educational process commences from pregnancy.

Based on a sociocultural approach, family functions at least include biological functions, educative functions, religious functions, protective functions, socialization functions, recreative functions, and economic functions (Sudjana, 2012:87).

Building on the explanations, family education constitutes education breaking out within a family, wherein parents should conduct their tasks and responsibilities for educating their children within their families. Additionally, it is a behavioral and attitude transformation process in a group or the smallest social unit in the community, heralded by the indicators of biological functions, educative functions, religious functions, protective functions, socialization functions, recreative functions, and economic functions.

2.4. Community Attitude

Gerungan (2014:160) elaborates on the definition of attitudes, i.e., a view or emotion of individuals as a reaction to a certain object. Although the object is the same, some individuals may not share the same attitudes. The reaction can be impacted by individual conditions, experiences, information, and needs. Individual attitudes toward an object will give off individual behaviors toward the object.

Sarlito & Eko (2019:152-154) elucidate attitude formation: 1) classical conditioning: This formation process comes about when a stimulus is always followed by another one, making the first stimulus a cue of the next one, 2) instrumental conditioning: A specific behavior will be recurrent if the learning process implemented lead to a pleasing result. Nevertheless, when a particular behavior induces an adverse outcome, the behavior will be avoided, 3) Learning by observing: This learning process is implemented by observing others, and 4) Social comparison: This learning process is implemented by comparing others to check whether our views of a certain object is correct.

Basically, community attitudes constitute an interrelation of a range of components. Allport suggests the three forms of the components, i.e., cognitive, affective, and conative components.

Grounded on the explanation above, community attitudes are a reaction or response in the form of individual judgment of a particular object marked by cognition, affection, and conation indicators.

2.5. Research Hypothesis

On the grounds of the research framework, the research hypotheses are:

- Government roles positively affect community attitudes in Gorontalo City.
- Family education positively affects community attitudes in Gorontalo City.
- Positive attitudes positively affect juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City.
- Government roles positively affect juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City.
- Family education positively affects community attitudes in Gorontalo City
- Government roles, family education, and community attitudes positively and simultaneously affect juvenile delinquency.

3. Research Method

A survey method with quantitative data and path analysis technique was used to disclose the influence between variables. This research had independent variables (government roles (X1), family education (X2), and community attitudes (X3)) and an independent one (juvenile delinquency (Y)).

The samples were part of the investigated population. Samples constituted part of a particular population focus. I used the probability sampling technique using Slovin's formula, i.e., performing sampling by measuring error levels which would happen in a sampling activity, resulting in 99 samples.

Data were collected through questionnaires using a Likert scale. The data analysis used descriptive and inferential statistical analyses.

4. Results and Discussion

Result interpretation referred to the results of six hypothesis tests: (a) the effect of government roles on community attitudes, (b) the effect of family education on community attitudes, (c) the effect of government roles on juvenile delinquency, (d) the effect of family education of juvenile delinquency, (e) the effect of community attitudes on juvenile delinquency, (f) the simultaneous effect of government roles, family education, and community attitudes on juvenile delinquency in Gorontalo City.

4.1. The Effect of Government Roles on Community Attitudes

Predicated on the acquired regression equation $= 30,065 + 0.782X_1$, an increase in the government role score was followed by an increase in the community attitude score, or a higher government role would produce a higher community attitude. From the coefficient of determination (r^2) = 0.620, 62.0% of the community attitude variation could be explained by government roles, whereas 38.0% was explicated by other factors. It could underlie the argumentation that community attitudes were determined by multiple factors, e.g., government roles. Even if government roles had a relatively medium impact of 62.0% on community attitudes, statistically, the impact was significant and in so doing, should not be disregarded.

Awaludin, in Prasojo (2015:18), classifies many different government roles into three groups, i.e., a) Regulating function, including policy-making, orientation, guidance, regulation through permission, and monitoring, b) Owner of economic or social businesses, either self- or private-implemented, and c) Self-implementation of various economic or social activities.

Government roles related to development are delivering development-related messages, directing the community to participate, and responding to community aspirations. The roles have many contributions, especially in augmenting community participation and empowerment. That being so, government roles related to community attitudes cover the roles of pioneer, innovator, facilitator, stabilizer, and mediator for the various interests of the people it regulates. Associated with development, the roles should be interrelated.

4.2. The Effect of Family Education on Community Attitudes

Based on the acquired regression equation $= 24,764 + 0.827X_2$, an increase in the family education score was followed by an increase in the community attitude score, or a higher government role would result in a higher community attitude. Building on the coefficient of determination (r^2) = 0.718, 71.8% of the community attitude variation could be illuminated by family education, while 28.2% was laid out by other factors. It could underlie the argumentation that community attitudes were determined by myriad factors, e.g., family education. Even though family education had a relatively medium impact of 71.8% on community attitudes, statistically, the impact was significant and in so doing, should not be forgone.

The results demonstrated that communities, to build a linkage within a relationship in which they could contribute to each other, had duty and family right networking, called a role relationship. Attributed to family, to establish a good one, family members should interact with each other, run responsibilities and rights, and contribute, implementing effective family roles. The family education concept offered the cruciality of child characteristics and behaviors. The concept, therefore, was imperative to reminding us of the potencies of individual intelligence and behavioral bases to be formed in this age span.

The questionnaire-generated results exhibited a low family role related to child education. Families indicated a lack of harmony, and parents set purposes not according with child education. Among the solution was by elevating an educative interaction between parents and children, adhering to the theory that family played an important part in child development.

4.3. The Effect of Community Attitudes on Juvenile Delinquency

On the grounds of the acquired regression equation $15,103 + 0.822X_3$, an increase in the community attitude score was followed by an increase in the juvenile delinquency score, or a higher community attitude would result in higher juvenile delinquency. Predicated on the coefficient of determination (r^2) = 0.653, 65.3% of the juvenile delinquency variation could be set forth by community attitudes, while 34.7% was shed light on by other factors. It could underlie the argumentation that juvenile delinquency was determined by a multitude of factors, e.g., community attitudes. Though community attitudes had a relatively medium influence of 65.3% on juvenile delinquency, statistically, the influence was significant and, thus, should not be ignored.

According to Panai et al. (2022:57), involving adolescents in community activities, known as role-playing, could decrease juvenile delinquency rates. An integrative media mode, integrated with role-playing media, was considered commensurate with the program targets, i.e., children and their families at home. The role-playing method was applied to enable the target groups to understand the playing materials well. The interactive mode could give learning experiences, abilities to cooperate, communicativeness, and abilities to interpret an event. Additionally, it could enhance the abilities, skills, attitudes of the target groups related to their social life, and interaction with the universe.

As pointed out by the results, community attitudes constituted an organization of individual opinions and beliefs related to a relatively specific object or situation, accompanied by certain feelings, and fostering the individual to give a response or present behavior in a particular manner they chose. Attitudes developed within one's self (and becoming his/her part of life) were apt to retain and difficult to alter. Changing baseline attitudes referred to carrying out a new adaptation to the object or situation being put up with.

4.4. The Effect of Government Roles on Juvenile Delinquency

From the acquired regression equation $37,591 + 0.664X_1$, an increase in the government role score was followed by an increase in the juvenile delinquency score, or a higher government role would yield higher juvenile delinquency. Based on the coefficient of determination (r^2) = 0.432, 43.2% of the juvenile delinquency variation could be spelled out by government roles, while 56.8% was elucidated by other factors. It could underlie the argumentation that juvenile delinquency was determined by a plethora of factors, e.g., government roles. Though government roles had a relatively medium impact of 43.2% on juvenile delinquency, statistically, the impact was significant and, thus, should not be neglected.

An indispensable activity in determining a successful program for combating juvenile delinquency was optimized service delivery. Public service principles, according to MENPAN No. 63/KEP/M.PAN/7/2003, were: a) simple, understandable, and feasible procedures for public services delivery, b) clear technical and administrative requirements for public services delivery, work units, or officials authorized and responsible for providing services and responding to complaints, problems, and disputes related to public service implementation, details of public service costs, and payment procedures, c) certain timeline for implementing public services, which were expected to be delivered within a set period, d) the accuracy of public service products, which should be correctly, precisely, and legally delivered, e) public service process and product safety, and thereby, giving the sense of security and legal certainties, f) responsibilities of public service implementor directors or officials assigned for being responsible for service implementation and complaint or issue following-up related to public service implementation, g) sufficient provision of facilities, work infrastructures, and so on, covering technology, telecommunication, and information facilities, h) accessibility, embodied by adequate and accessible service sites and facilities for the community using technology, telecommunication, and information, i) discipline, civility, friendliness, and sincerity in service delivery, and j) convenient service environment, which accordingly, should be orderly and organized. Comfortable, clean, neat waiting rooms, an idyllic and healthy environment, supporting facilities, e.g., parking lots, toilets, praying rooms, and the like, should be provided. Public service implementation should have service standards published as insurance for certainties for service receivers (Djafri, 2018:21-22).

The results showed that juvenile delinquency could be investigated from several factors, such as hereditary, psychological, environmental, family, urbanization, unemployment, and symptoms of the end times. Juvenile delinquency was not caused by biological factors, but hereditary ones had a great impact, especially related to the inherited traits, e.g., weak minds and neurosis. Due to these traits, the impacted children would lack abilities to self-adjust, learn, and appreciate moral values. Other impacted children might have excessive energy and were full of spirit, making them seem highly active, oppressive, and fond of fighting.

4.5. The Effect of Family Education on Juvenile Delinquency

From the acquired regression equation $17,482 + 0.849X_2$, an increase in the family education score was followed by an increase in the juvenile delinquency score, or a higher family education would yield higher juvenile delinquency. Based on the coefficient of determination (r^2) = 0.730, 73.0% of the juvenile delinquency variation could be explained by family education, while 27.0% was explicated by other factors. It could underlie the argumentation that juvenile delinquency was determined by a preponderance of factors, e.g., family education. Although family education had a relatively medium influence of 73.0% on juvenile delinquency, statistically, the influence was significant and, thus, should not be overlooked.

As suggested by the results, the community believed that religious education and values delivered since childhood could prevent and de-escalate the negative risks of adolescence. Religious development in childhood was manifested through the life experiences of children living in family, school, and community environments. The more the religious experiences (comporting with religious teachings) and elements, the more conforming the attitudes, actions, behaviors, and manners of confronting the life of children to religious teachings.

4.6. The Simultaneous Effect of Government Roles, Family Education, and Community Attitudes on Juvenile Delinquency

From the acquired regression equation $12,259 + 0.183X_1 + 0.681X_2 + 0.3769X_3$, an increase in the government role, family education, and community attitude score was followed by an increase in the juvenile delinquency score, or higher government roles, family education, and community attitudes would breed higher juvenile delinquency. Building on the coefficient of determination (r^2) = 0.766, 76.6% of the juvenile delinquency variation could be explained by government roles, family education, and community attitudes, while 23.4% was illuminated by other factors. It could underlie the argumentation that juvenile delinquency was determined by a raft of factors, e.g., government roles, family education, and community attitudes. Although government roles, family education, and community attitudes had a relatively medium influence of 76.6% on juvenile delinquency, statistically, the influence was significant and, thus, should not be abandoned.

The family, school, and community should be supportive of adolescent ability escalation by creating a conducive house, school, village, or urban village environment. This support could impel adolescents to heighten their intellectual capability for socializing. Adolescent capacities of understanding, planning, carrying out, and making solutions to a range of issues were the objectives of family education delivered in family and community environments (Hulukati & Nadjamuddin, 2022:987-996).

The results demonstrated that juvenile delinquency was ever-increasingly unsettling. Juvenile delinquency was not necessarily grounded on the personal desires of adolescents. Instead, it might be impacted by their environment and served as their protests and efforts to exhibit their existence to parents or the community which might have treated them unfairly.

4.7. Research Novelty

On the grounds of the results, government roles, family education, and community attitudes had a positive influence, partial or simultaneous, on juvenile delinquency. Government roles, family education, and community attitudes affected juvenile delinquency by 43.2%, 73%, and 65.3%, respectively. Family education, followed by community attitudes, was identified as having the most significant effect. As such, family education within the community environment should be improved predicated on government regulations.

A collaboration between the government, families, and the community was key to successful programs to cope with juvenile delinquency. As such, the research novelty was oriented to a collaborative pattern, or *tolongala'a* in the Gorontalo language, to deal with juvenile delinquency.

Tolongala'a meant togetherness as a family. Bearing on our discussion, hence, juvenile delinquency was the responsibility of many different parties: the adolescents concerned, parents, all community components, and the government. Among the solutions to juvenile delinquency was raising shared awareness that responsibilities for educating and guiding adolescents should be held by adolescents per se, parents, the community, and the government. The government was expecting cooperation between various parties to get a maximum outcome related to juvenile delinquency prevention.

Figure 1 indicates the *tolongala'a* model to eradicate juvenile delinquency developed in this research.

Figure 1 Research Novelty, *Tolongala'a*, to Mitigate Juvenile Delinquency and Create Quality Adolescents

5. Conclusion

From the results, I could draw some conclusions as follows:

- Government roles had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 62% on community attitudes. In so doing, the higher the government roles, the higher the community attitudes.
- Family education had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 71.8% on community attitudes. In so doing, the higher the family education, the higher the community attitudes.
- Community attitudes had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 65.3% on juvenile delinquency. In so doing, the higher the community attitudes, the lower the juvenile delinquency.
- Government roles had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 43.2% on juvenile delinquency. In so doing, the higher the government roles, the lower the juvenile delinquency.
- Family education had a direct, positive, and significant effect of 73% on juvenile delinquency. In so doing, the higher the family education, the lower the juvenile delinquency.
- Government roles, family education, and community attitudes had a simultaneous, direct, positive, and significant effect of 76.6% on juvenile delinquency. In so doing, the higher the government roles, family education, and community attitude, the lower the juvenile delinquency.

An implication constitutes a direct consequence of scientific research results. This research addresses the effect of government roles, family education, and community attitudes on juvenile delinquency. Based on the results, government roles, family education, and community attitudes affect juvenile delinquency.

That being so, the research implications are as follows:

1. Government Roles

Several attempts which can increase government roles in overcoming juvenile delinquency are:

○ Strict Monitoring at Schools

At this juncture, adolescents spend the most time at school. Therefore, the government should conduct strict monitoring at schools. For instance, it can perform routine raids on students to find objects the students are prohibited from being held or carried at schools.

○ Parental and School Engagement

In addition, students also spend time at home, thereby requiring parental roles to reduce juvenile delinquency. Therefore, parental roles in preventing juvenile delinquency must be activated.

○ Anti-Juvenile Delinquency Campaigns

The government should routinely hold campaign activities under the theme of tackling juvenile delinquency. It should involve adolescents from different educational levels. Delivering knowledge to adolescents related to the no benefit of delinquency needs to be prioritized.

- **Socializing Related to the Danger of Juvenile Delinquency**

Besides campaigns, the government implements socialization concerning the danger of juvenile delinquency. Exposures to the danger-related knowledge will give warnings to adolescents germane to no benefit of delinquency.

- **Activating Many Extracurricular Activities at Schools**

To avoid outside-school activities with no use and the potencies of juvenile delinquency, the government applies a range of extracurricular activities students can participate in. This activity can upgrade the non-academic skills of students. As a result, besides academic skills, students can master arts, sports, or other useful activities. These activities can also cultivate the non-academic potencies and skills of children.

- **Moral Education Delivery**

Moral education helps students differentiate between good and bad activities. Good moral and character building will cut the number of juvenile delinquency cases.

- **Religious Effect Corroboration**

Religions are paramount elements in constraining adolescent behaviors. Fears of sins since childhood will usually remain until adulthood. As such, religious education should be delivered from childhood.

- **Community Attitudes**

The community, where adolescents socialize and carry out activities, can conduct the following preventive actions against juvenile delinquency.

- **Monitoring**

The community should monitor all activities of the adolescents living in its environment. The community can file a report to parents or responsible parties if any activities leading to juvenile delinquency are identified.

- **Giving Guidance/Socialization Concerning Juvenile Delinquency**

The community should give direct or indirect guidance and socialization in connection with juvenile delinquency.

- **Sweeping Juvenile Delinquency Sites**

The community can perform this activity with the responsible parties to gain an optimum result.

- **Coordinating with Schools to Strictly Sanction/Punish Truant Students**

The community can inform schools if catching truant students who commit delinquency.

- **Family Education**

Family, as where children come from, should undertake the following actions.

- Modeling (giving examples of trustworthiness): Parents are the first role models for children. How children think and behave complies with how their parents think and behave. Through modeling, children will learn how to show proactiveness, respect, and affection.
- Mentoring: Mentoring is the ability to build a relationship, emotional investment (affection to others), protection for others, honesty, and unconditionality. Profoundness, honesty, and sincerity in protecting will induce others to act openly and accept learning voluntarily based on trust. Parents are the first sources of emotional development in children.
- Organizing: Organizing relates to fulfilling family needs through teamwork and cooperation between family members. All tasks are carried out together.

- Teaching: Basic laws of life should be delivered to family members. Parents, in relation to their teacher roles, should bring about a conscious competence in children. Children should experience what they are doing and understand the reason for it.

Based on the conclusions and implications, I can give the following suggestions to the parties concerned.

- The Gorontalo City government should optimize policies pertaining to juvenile delinquency by promoting family education and community attitudes and continuously adjusting policies to human civilization development.
- The community has to cooperate with families and the government to guide and develop adolescents through community and development activities.
- Families should provide family education continuously by giving good examples and showing good habits to children, making them accustomed to positive deeds.
- Adolescents should scale up self-quality by avoiding promiscuity, alcohol, drugs, wild racing, free sex, theft, and others.

Suggestion

Future researchers should follow up this research by performing similar research and developing independent variables, the number of respondents, and research site coverage because there are still a wealth of factors impacting juvenile delinquency besides government roles, family education, and community attitudes.

Compliance with ethical standards

Disclosure of conflict of interest

No conflict of interest.

References

- [1] Aziz, A. 2015. "Pendidikan Agama dalam Keluarga: Tantangan Era Globalisasi". Himmah, Jurnal Ilmiah Keagamaan dan Kemasyarakatan, Vol. 6, No. 15.
- [2] Djafri, N. 2018. Manajemen Pelayanan (Berbasis Revolusi Mental). Gorontalo: Ideas Publishing.
- [3] Fatih, A. M. 2014. Peta Konsep Desentralisasi dan Pemerintah Daerah. Surabaya: ITS Prees.
- [4] Gerungan. 2014. Psikologi Sosial. Bandung: Rafika Aditama.
- [5] Hasan, B. 2019. "Pendidikan Anak dalam Keluarga: Telaah Epistemologis". Pedagogik: Jurnal Pendidikan, Vol. 3, No. 2.
- [6] Hasan, L. 2016. Manusia dan Pendidikan. Jakarta: Al-Husna Zikra.
- [7] Hasanah, N. & Fauzi, A. 2016. Akuntansi Pemerintahan. Jakarta: In Media.
- [8] Hulukati, E. A. N. 2022. "Kemampuan Literasi Numerasi Mahasiswa dalam Menyelesaikan Masalah Matematika", JURNALBASICEDU, Vol 6, No. 1, pp. 987-996.
- [9] Kartono. 2017. Personality, Employee Engagement, Emotional Intelligence, Job Burnout dalam Melihat Turnover Intention. Yogyakarta: CV Budi Utama.
- [10] PanaI, A. H., Cuga, C., Adhani, Y., Ardini, P. P., Sarlin, M., Handayani, S., & Alfitriah, S. 2022. Mitigasi Bencana Berbasis Moda Media Interaktif (MMI) pada Masyarakat Desa Tupa, Kabupaten Bone Bolango. p-ISSN/e-ISSN: 2798-6624/2809-5863.
- [11] Prasojo, R. A. & Fauziah, L. 2015. "Peran Pemerintah-Masyarakat dalam Pembangunan Desa Sedatigede Kecamatan Sedati Kabupaten Sidoarjo". JKMP (ISSN. 2338-445X), Vol. 3, No. 1, pp. 1-116.
- [12] Sarlito, W. & Meinarno, E. A. 2019. Psikologi Sosial. Jakarta: Salemba.
- [13] Sujana, D. 2012. Peran Keluarga di Lingkungan Masyarakat dalam Keluarga Muslim dalam Masyarakat Modern. Bandung: Remaja Rosyda Karya.
- [14] Yusuf, I. 2014. Teori dan Praktik Pemerintahan dan Otonomi Daerah. Jakarta: PT Gramedia Widiasarana Indonesia.